

SIGNIFICANCE OF ALEKSANRDR FAINBERG’S LITERARY WORK

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Abstrakt: This article provides detailed information about the life and creative path of Aleksandr Arkadevich Feinberg, who, although originally Russian, made a great contribution to Uzbek poetry and has a deep place in the hearts of the Uzbek people. At the same time, the importance of Feinberg's legacy and the conveyance of the poet's ideas to young readers are considered. It is said about his translations, which have a worthy place in his work. Although he is a Russian-speaking poet, the work of the poet, who does not fade from the heart of the Uzbek nation, is promoted to young artists.

Keywords: Translation activity, rare works, Uzbek nation, poetry collection, "Rubai tori", "Yangi Volga"

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о жизненном и творческом пути Александра Аркадьевича Файнберга, который, хотя и русский по происхождению, внес большой вклад в узбекскую поэзию и занимает глубокое место в сердцах узбекского народа. При этом рассматривается значение наследия Файнберга и донесения идей поэта до юных читателей. Говорится о его переводах, которые занимают достойное место в его творчестве. Хотя он и русскоязычный поэт, творчество поэта, не угасающее в сердце узбекской нации, пропагандируется среди молодых художников.

Ключивый слова: Переводческая деятельность, редкие произведения, узбекский народ, поэтические сборники, «Рубай тории», «Янги Волга».

Alexander Fainberg Arkadevich is one of the poets who entered Uzbek poetry in the second half of the last century. It is worth mentioning his creative journey. The poet is the author of more than 20 cartoons for children, several prose works and more than 15 poetry collections. His works were translated into the Uzbek language, his texts were sung by singers, his poems and collections were eagerly awaited and read.

It is worth mentioning that a number of films based on Fainberg's screenplays were created in the "Uzbektelefilm" film studio and were popularly watched. For example, "My brother", "Finds in Kandahar", "Under the hot sun" are among them. Based on his scripts, not only "Uzbektelefilm", but also "Criminals and Acquittals" films were created at the "Tajikfilm" film studio. Through the epic "Rubai tori" which

belongs to the series of comic works, he skillfully described Uzbek teahouses and won a deep place in the hearts of the people. "Far Bridges", "Response"(1982), "Short Wave"(1983), "Spreading Net"(1984), "Free Sonnets"(1990), "Etude"(1967), "Sonia" (1969), "Poems" (1977) poems and poetry collections are still read with love. It is gratifying that many of the writer's rare works of his time were published in foreign countries such as Israel and Canada.

The sharp poet occupies an important place in the field of translation with his translations. He is considered one of the skilled translators and made a worthy contribution to the promotion of Uzbek poetry by translating Uzbek works into Russian. Examples of these are Erkin Vahidov's poem "Rebellion of the Spirits" published in Moscow, and the collection of translations of the works of Uzbek poets called "Aqqushlar gala" published in Tashkent. In addition to these, the translator skilfully translated poems and epics of famous Uzbek poets E. Vahidov, A. Oripov, O. Matjon into Russian. Along with this, the ghazals of Alisher Navoi, the sultan of the ghazal estate, are no exception. These are not only translations, but they are the peak of the translator's translation activity. Rustam Musurman plays a major role in translating Feinberg's legacy to his descendants. A number of magazines such as "New World", "Youth", "Yangi Volga", "Change" contributed to the world view.

People's poet of Uzbekistan Alexander Arkadevich Fainberg made a worthy contribution to Uzbek poetry. Even after his death, two volumes of his collected works were published. He was awarded the Pushkin Medal in 2008. He died in 2009 in Tashkent. In order to preserve the memory of Feinberg, many works were carried out in Uzbekistan. For example, a statue of the poet was placed on the writer's avenue located in the capital, along with a number of other poets and writers of our country, and the "Feinberg Scholarship" was introduced in order to widely promote the poet's life and creativity among young people. Alexander Arkadevich Fainberg's work is an incomparable contribution to the development of our literature. The poet is a poet who was able to reflect the feelings of humanity and nationalism, gratitude and love for his homeland in his heritage. He is always alive in the hearts of Uzbek youth, poetry lovers and the nation.

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